

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF CORBETT NATIONAL PARK IN TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to examine the role of Corbett National Park in social and economic impacts in the tourism industry. This study elaborates on the various employment areas and their prospects in Corbett National Park. It will examine the number of employed persons working in Corbett National Park and their socio-economic status. Structured questionnaires and interview methods will be used for the collection of primary data. Secondary data will be collected from Corbett National Park and various journals and reports. The percentage method will be used to analyze the data. Results and findings will be presented through explanatory form, tables, and graphical presentation.

Keywords: Employment Generation, Tourism, Socio-economic status.

Introduction

Tourism is one of the sun-rising sectors with tremendous opportunities to create jobs in India. It contributes a larger share in employment generation. It also creates income and plays a vital role in the acceleration of the economic growth of the country. Rich cultural and natural heritage, as historical and religious places, attract international tourist arrivals (ITAs) to India. However, the Tourism sector in India is underutilized. India's tourism sector is growing rapidly over the time period. India's tourism economy is 4th largest in the world and it ranked at 40th position in The World Travel & Tourism Council (WT& TC) report 2017. The WT & TC has calculated that tourism generated INR 14, 018.5 bn, recorded 9.6% of GDP in 2016. It generated 40,343,000 thousand jobs and contributed 9.3% of total employment. The sector is predicted to grow at an average annual rate of 7.9% from 2013 to 2023. Uttarakhand state also has tremendous potential for tourist activities, especially in cultural tourism, religious tourism, leisure tourism, and wildlife tourism. Holy confluences, scenic surroundings, and an aura of spiritual serenity make an ideal abode for the Gods and are a refreshing reward for the pilgrims and tourists who visit Uttarakhand. Tourism is the fastest-

growing industry in Uttarakhand and affects the state economy in various ways. In wildlife tourism, Uttarakhand is one of the leading states in the country. It has many national parks which have a significant place to conserve wildlife all over the world. Jim Corbett National Park is one of them. It is the oldest national park in India and was established in 1936 as Hailey National Park to protect the endangered Bengal tiger. It is located in Nainital district and Pauri Garhwal district of Uttarakhand and was named after Jim Corbett, a well-known hunter and naturalist. The park was the first to come under the Project Tiger initiative. The park has sub-Himalayan belt geographical and ecological characteristics. An ecotourism destination, it contains 488 different species of plants and a diverse variety of fauna. The increase in tourist activities, among other problems, continues to present a serious challenge to the park's ecological balance. Corbett has been a haunt for tourists and wildlife lovers for a long time. Tourism activity is only allowed in selected areas of Corbett Tiger Reserve so that people get an opportunity to see its landscape and wildlife. In recent years the number of people coming here has increased dramatically. Presently, every season more than 70,000 visitors come to the park. It employs in various areas in which numerous personnel work for the Corbett National Park. The present study analyses the different employment areas in Corbett National Park and number of employees working in these areas and their socio-economic status.

Objectives of the Study

- To study and analyze the various tourism areas of employment in Corbett National Park
- To study and analyze the number of personnel working in Corbett National Park.
- To study and analyze the socio-economic status of the people working in Corbett National Park.

Research Methodology

(i) Sample:

The present study is based on primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from the taxi drivers, guides, and forest guards working in Corbett National Park, and the secondary data collected from the head office of Corbett National Park, Ramnagar (Uttarakhand).

(ii) Data Collection Tool:

Primary data has been collected by structured Questionnaire containing objective-type questions. Secondary data were collected from the head office of Corbett National Park.

(iii) Statistical Tool:

Graphical presentation and tables were used to show the findings and results.

Results And Findings

The main purpose of the present study was to investigate the major employment areas in Corbett National Park and the number of personnel working for it. To analyze the socio-economic status of employees, the primary data have been taken through a questionnaire. On this basis, the Major findings are given below:

1. Various Employment areas in Corbett National Park:

2. Number of personnel working in Corbett National Park in various areas:

S.No.	Areas	Number of workers
1.	No. of Taxies registered	259
2.	Forests Guides	94
3.	Official Staff	
	Group A	3
	Group B	15
	Group C	231
	Group D	47
	Total	296
4.	Forests Watcher temporarily	420

3. Socio-economic Status of the workers:

For Forests Watcher:

- (a) Circle Rate approved by Corbett National Park Rs. 6,344.00 per month
- (b) Under RIT Rs. 7,000 per month
- (c) Putilal v/s State Rs. 9,913 per month

4. Tariff for Jungle Safari approved by Corbett Tiger Reserve:

S.No.	For day visit (4 hours)	₹		
	Bijrani	2,000		
	Jhirna	2,200		
	Dhela	2,200		
	Durgadevi	2,200		
	For night stay	1 Night	2 Nights	3 Nights
		₹	₹	₹
	Dhikala	4,800	7,000	9,000
	Gairal	5,200	7,500	9,500
	Sultan	5,200	7,500	9,500
	Sarpduli	5,200	7,500	9,500
	Bijrani	3,800	5,500	7,500
	Jhirna	4,000	6,000	7,500
	Malani	4,500	6,500	8,000
	Sonanadi	5,000	9,000	12,000

5. Night Stay in Corbett National Park (Forest Rest House)

Corbett National Park is divided into four Eco-Tourism Zone for night stay:

BIJRANI ZONE		
	No. of Rooms	Type of Room
Bijrani (FRH)	4	Double Bed
	2	Single Bed
	4	Dormitory
Malani (FRH)	2	Double Bed

SONANADI ECO-TOURISM ZONE		
	No. of Rooms	Type of Room
Halparao (FRH)	2	Double Bed
Rathuwadhab (FRH)	2	Double Bed
Mudiapani (FRH)	2	Double Bed

DHIKALA ECO-TOURISM ZONE		
	No. of Rooms	Type of Room
Dhikala (FRH)	6	Hutment (Double Bed)
	3	Cabin (Double Bed)
	4	New FRH (Double Bed)
	5	Old FRH (Double Bed)
	7	Annexi (Double Bed)
	12	Dormitory
Gairal (FRH)	4	New FRH (Double Bed)
	8	Dormitory
Sarpduli	2	FRH (Double Bed)
	3	Dormitory
Sultan	2	FRH (Double Bed)

JHIRNA ECO-TOURISM ZONE		
	No. of Rooms	Type of Room
Jhirna(FRH)	2	Double Bed
	1	Double Bed

Conclusion

This study revealed that:

- Corbett National Park provides various employment areas to the people and many people earn the money for their survival.
- The socio-economic status of the watcher is satisfactory but the tariff for jungle safari is good for the drivers.
- Forest Tiger Reserve also offers various types of rest houses for night stays.
- It has been also observed that the attraction of tourists towards the Corbett National Park and wildlife tourism from the last few years has increased in comparison to other tourist areas.

Suggestions

After the study, It is to be suggested that:

- The working position of the watcher should be permanent. Irregularity leads to job dissatisfaction among them.
- The circle rate for the fire watcher is very low. Corbett National Park should provide an adequate amount of remuneration to them with which their socio-economic status can be improved.
- The 165 posts out of the 461 in Corbett National Park in groups A, B, C, and D are vacant. These posts should not be vacant. On the one hand, It shows weak administrative control and on another hand, people are left deprived of employment opportunities.

References

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